

IMPROVING STUDENTS' INSTRUMENTAL PERFORMANCE SKILLS (EXAMPLE OF DUTAR)

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Abstract

The thesis is dedicated to the issues of improving students' instrumental performance skills using the dutar instrument as an example. The author studies pedagogical methods aimed at developing students' technical, musical, and creative abilities. The work examines various aspects of learning to play the instrument, including hand placement, developing coordination, auditory control, and mastering the musical repertoire. Special attention is given to the gradual transition to standard instrumental playing using a student instrument. The author emphasizes the importance of an individual approach to education, considering each student's age, ability, and interest. Effective teaching methods such as exercises, etudes, and excerpts are regarded as the key to successfully mastering the instrument.

Keywords

Dutar, instrumental performance, skill development, pedagogical methods, technique

Introduction

Relevance of the study. As a field of sound and musical imagery, music has a unique impact on the emotional world of a person, affecting their thoughts and feelings and contributing to their understanding of the purpose of life. It evokes feelings of beauty and goodness, love and freedom. Under the influence of the art of music, a spiritual ideal of personality is formed, which helps to resist the destructive power of evil, endure difficult situations and trials.

In modern musical culture, popular music performed with symphonic, pop, and wind instruments such as trumpets, horns, trombones, clarinets, saxophones, and others play a significant role. These are the most important components of the music and performance culture of our time.

In our research, we focused on the preparation of dutar musicians, improving the musical performance skills of young performers in higher educational institutions of culture and art, and paying attention to various schools and

musical directions in this regard. The psychological principles of mastering the skills and abilities necessary for playing and listening to music, the conditions for improving the teaching and educational process, and the problems of identifying musical talent are studied by the psychology of music education and upbringing. We find a deep interconnection between music and psychology in the monographs of V. M. Teplov, V. V. Nazaykinsky, and V. V. Medushevsky.

Performers can divide their work into three stages:

1. Stage of familiarization with the musical piece – the stage of forming the concept of performance;
2. Stage of implementing the performance plan;
3. Stage of pre-performance preparation.

The method depends on many conditions:

- The musician's level of maturity and talent;
- How familiar the piece is;
- The relevance of the task, the attitude towards the piece ("cold" or "passionate");
- Its complexity and degree of technical difficulty, among others.

Numerous studies by methodologists and psychologists show that to effectively assimilate educational material, the student must engage in special cognitive (gnostic) activities aimed at processing the received information.

There are various classifications of methods proposed by famous educators in didactics such as I.Ya, M.N. Davydov, and others[1].

Our methods of teaching the dutar include:

1. Visual method (when the teacher directly demonstrates any performance technique on the instrument to the student);
2. Verbal method (the teacher explains the laws of art, helping the student to reflect the character of the performed piece using figurative comparisons);
3. The method of "actions according to the model" (reproductive method) – helps the student find their "own," "individual" way through copying or imitation;

We classify the artistic-heuristic (search) method as a problematic method when the teacher searches for individual performance techniques based on the student's capabilities.

Many performers detail their techniques and tools to achieve the necessary calm before a performance. This is a result of the unique nature of a natural and creative individual.

Find a piece that most strongly reveals the student's individuality and matches the performer's taste. The complexity of the pieces in the concert repertoire should correspond to the student's level of development to form psychological preparation for the performance. The teacher must ensure that the student achieves technical mastery, which is the most important condition for solving the assigned performance task.

The teacher's task is to develop the student's desire to communicate with the audience and the abilities necessary for such communication. The teacher should provide methodological assistance in the students' independent work: create a plan for working on the piece, a plan for interpreting the piece, and a plan for public performance, as well as give recommendations for autotraining during the preparation period. It is essential to form an optimal state of preparation in students comprehensively. This includes eliminating physical and mental stress in students.

Applying and identifying a set of techniques is crucial:

- Working "in the mind" and on the instrument.
- Psychological preparation for the situation: you need to start mental work before your fingers touch the keys.
- Modeling working conditions in the mind – mentally imagining working conditions on stage.
- Use psychotherapeutic methods: persuasion, condemnation, abstract conversation, and others.

Developing Technical Skills

Developing technical skills is fundamental for successfully mastering any musical instrument. For playing the dutar, proper hand placement, finger positioning, and movement coordination are crucial. The student dutar is smaller and has lighter strings, making it suitable for developing beginners' techniques. Specially designed exercises for the student dutar help develop finger dexterity, coordination, and strength. Regular practice of these exercises creates a solid foundation for further skill improvement.

Forming Auditory Control

Auditory control plays an essential role in playing any musical instrument. Students need to learn to distinguish pitch, rhythm, and dynamics. The student dutar allows students to develop their auditory skills in a more controlled and comfortable environment. Teachers can use the student dutar to demonstrate various musical intervals, rhythmic patterns, and dynamic nuances. Students can

practice playing simple melodies and accompaniments by ear, helping them develop a sense of accurate intonation and rhythm.

Mastering the Musical Repertoire

Gradual mastery of the musical repertoire is a critical aspect of learning to play the dutar. Beginner students should start with simple pieces and gradually move on to more complex ones. The student dutar allows students to perform music that matches their level of technical preparation and musical development. Teachers can use the student dutar to introduce students to various musical genres and styles. Learning folk songs, classical works, and contemporary compositions can broaden students' musical horizons and develop their artistic taste.

Gradual Transition to Standard Instrument Playing

The student dutar plays a significant role in students' gradual transition to standard instrument playing. As students develop technical skills and musical understanding, they can gradually increase the size and tension of the dutar strings, approaching the standard instrument specifications. This gradual transition allows students to adapt to changes in string size, weight, and tension, as well as the wide range of sound and timbre. The student dutar serves as a bridge between initial preparation and full performance on the standard dutar. Additionally, using the student dutar helps overcome the psychological barrier associated with switching to a new instrument. Students can feel more confident when they start playing the standard dutar, knowing they have mastered the basic skills and repertoire.

The Role of Technology in Skill Improvement

Technology plays an essential role in improving students' dutar playing skills. Digital tuners and metronomes help students develop a sense of accurate intonation and rhythm. Recording devices allow students to analyze their performance and identify areas for improvement. Online resources such as video tutorials and interactive exercises can complement traditional teaching methods. Students can access materials at any time and place, making the learning process more flexible and engaging. However, it is important to note that technology should not replace face-to-face communication with the teacher. Teachers play a crucial role in providing personal instruction, motivation, and support to students.

Recommendations

1. Organize complete and necessary exercises in the classroom (hall), allowing the student to adapt to the instrument, and familiarize yourself with the lighting and acoustics in the hall.
2. Help the student understand the reasons for any difficulties during the performance process (if any) and create a program to overcome them. Enhance positive emotions.
3. The teacher should analyze the results of independent activities and the ways to achieve them, as well as carry out current and final monitoring based on diagnostics (i.e., using self-reflection technologies for personal development).
4. The final control, in the form of tests or exams, should generalize and systematize the student's skills and competencies, aiming to determine the formation level of the abilities and skills system for the section or course.

Conclusion

The student dutar is a valuable tool for improving students' dutar playing skills. It allows students to develop technical skills, auditory control, and master the musical repertoire more conveniently. Gradual transition to standard dutar playing, using technology, and teachers' individual approaches are the keys to successfully learning this wonderful instrument.

Creativity requires inspiration, and art requires skill. "...Skill is the ability to find figurative symbols of thoughts and ideas that are artistically perfect and irreproducible in their beauty." (D. D. Shostakovich) The author emphasizes the role of the student dutar as a means of gradual transition to standard instrumental playing. The author notes that using the student instrument allows students to develop proper techniques, improve auditory control, and master the musical repertoire more comfortably. In conclusion, the author hopes that the recommendations presented in the article will help teachers and students achieve significant success in improving their dutar playing skills. The author calls for further research into the pedagogy of teaching musical instruments to develop more effective teaching methods and make music education more accessible to everyone.

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